

MEDICAL SCIENCES

USING SUPERB MICROVASCULAR IMAGING TECHNOLOGY IN DETECTING BREAST SMALL FIBROADENOMA

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Abstract

Superb microvascular imaging (SMI) is a relatively recently developed ultrasound diagnostic technology that aims to visualize blood flow in blood vessels at low velocity and small diameter. Unlike conventional Color/ Power Doppler imaging, SMI can suppress the noise caused by motion artifacts without removing the weak signal from small blood flow, thus achieving higher sensitivity than duplex scanning.

A clinical case of a 33-year-old woman who has been unsuccessfully treated for 6 months for non-lactational mastitis caused by a small-sized mixed fibroadenoma that compresses and involves the gland duct is presented. Repeatedly performed ultrasound in B-mode + duplex scanning made it possible to diagnose dilation of the duct with its inhomogeneous contents, however, due to the resolving capabilities of the ultrasound scanner, it didn't allow visualizing the tumor. And only the use of SMI technology made it possible to intraductally localize the area of hypervascularization from microvessels, suspicious of neoplastic blood flow, which was later confirmed intraoperatively and morphologically verified as a tumor.

Keywords: small breast fibroadenoma, retentional enlargement of the lactiferous duct, non-lactational mastitis, ultrasound, SMI technology, surgical treatment.

Superb microvascular imaging (SMI) (or microvascular flow imaging (MVI/MV-flow) - the name varies depending on the manufacturer) is a relatively recently developed ultrasound diagnostic technology that aims to visualize blood flow in blood vessels at low speed and small diameter. Unlike conventional Color and Power Doppler imaging, SMI can suppress noise caused by motion artifacts without eliminating the weak signal generated by blood flow in small vessels, thus achieving higher sensitivity than duplex scanning [1, p.4].

SMI technology is based on an intelligent algorithm that (Fig. 1):

- distinguishes signals reflected from the blood flow and artifacts of tissue movement;
- preserves low-velocity blood flow components without loss of image quality (when using traditional methods, they are removed to avoid background noise);
- during visualization analyzes and removes interference - a more detailed picture of the vascular bed.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the ultrasound imaging possibility of blood flow in blood vessels with low speed and small diameter: a – traditional Doppler imaging; b - SMI technology

Advantages of SMI [7, p.2]:

1. visualization of low-velocity flow;
2. high resolution;
3. minimal movement artifact;
4. high frame rate.

Due to the relative novelty of the SMI method, there is not enough convincing clinical evidence of its effectiveness. Existing research suggests that it can be used to:

- to characterize focal and diffuse lesions of the liver [2, p.332-334; 6, p.2917-2921; 11, 2812-2814; 16, p.722];
- evaluate the vascularization of cystic and solid kidney lesions [9, p.9; 11, p.1954];
- evaluate the vascularization of breast lesions [11, p. 2814-2815; 16, p.724; 18, p.3-6]
- evaluate the blood supply to the thyroid nodes [10, p.10; 11, p. 2815-2816; 16, p.724];
- detect increased vascularization in tendons, joint capsules and peripheral nerves of the musculoskeletal system, allowing more sensitive [11, p. 2816-2817; 16, p.729];
- determine neovascularization within an atherosclerotic plaque in a vessel and thus assess the risk of hemorrhage into carotid plaques [11, p. 2817; 16, p.728].

Although breast cancers of different origins and sizes have different ultrasound appearances, a common feature is the presence of a large number of new blood vessels in the structure of the tumor, which are often not detected by conventional ultrasound. The appearance and development of breast cancer largely depend on the neovascularization in the tumor [5, p.E2]. Unlike clear collaterals with even vascular walls in benign tumors, neovascularization in malignant tumors is disorganized, the endothelial structure is incomplete, which is extremely important for tumor growth and metastasis [8, p.6]. Thus, the assessment of intratumoral neovascularization can provide important information for diagnosing the nature of the tumor and for determining the tactics of treatment. The gold standard for assessing tumor angiogenesis is microvessel density (MVD),

which is greater in malignant tumors than in benign ones. The higher the MVD, the greater the likelihood of metastasis [15, p.1782-1783]. Masses with abundant vessels and dense perforative flow are more likely to indicate malignancy on conventional ultrasonography. However, conventional ultrasound, especially in small tumors, often fails to detect microvessels because it is not sensitive to low-velocity flows within the tumor [3, p.306; 4, p.707]. SMI technology allows you to "see" these vessels. Studies have shown that SMI technology can provide more complete information about the blood flow that really exists in the tumor, offering important information for the diagnosis of breast cancer and is of great practical importance [13, p.5-6; 14, p.213; 17, p.2105; 19, p.921].

Thus, the use of SMI technology makes it possible to differentiate between benign and malignant tumors of the breast in cases where the ultrasound picture in B-mode + duplex scanning does not allow this. At the same time, we have not noted any works on the possibility of detecting focal lesions of the mammary gland of small sizes, involving and compressing the duct, against the background of inflammatory changes using SMI technology, in the literature at the moment.

We present our own **clinical case**.

Woman S., 33 years old, was admitted with complaints of pain, induration in the retroareolar region of the left breast, light straw discharge from the nipple of this gland.

Anamnesis. The patient first noted pain and scanty light straw discharge from the nipple of the left breast on January 28, 2023. She connected this with an acute respiratory viral disease. I turned to a mammologist at the place of residence on February 11, 2023. An ultrasound of the mammary glands and conservative treatment (Amoxiclav 1000 mg 2 times a day, Nimesil 1 time a day) were prescribed.

Mammary glands Ultrasound (3.03.2023). At 9 o'clock of the conventional dial, an anechoic elongated liquid lesion measuring 32x2 mm with an expanded interlobular space is determined. **Conclusion:** non-lactational mastitis on the left (BIRADS-3) (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Ultrasound image of changes in the left mammary gland

Due to the negative dynamics (the appearance of hyperemia of the skin of the nipple-areolar complex (NAC) of the left breast, as well as hemorrhagic discharge from the nipple), the patient turned to the surgeon at the place of residence (03.19.2023).

The diagnosis was made: non-lactational mastitis of the left mammary gland. Assigned: antibiotic therapy (Cifran 500 mg), local treatment (chlorhexidine solution).

Due to the weakly positive dynamics, but continuing pain in the left mammary gland, ultrasound of the mammary glands is recommended.

Mammary glands Ultrasound (29.04.2023): in the left mammary gland behind NAC liquid lesion up to 1 cm, with dense contents, pus?

It was decided to continue antibiotic therapy with a change in the drug (Amoxiclav 1000 mg 2 times a day) and a control mammary glands ultrasound in a week, as well as a study of the hormone prolactin.

Prolactin (4.05. 2023): within normal limits.

Mammary glands Ultrasound (4.05.2023): on the border of the lower quadrants of the left mammary gland along the edge of the areola, an enlarged lactiferous duct up to 4 mm is located with the lesion of a rounded liquid lesion up to 8 mm in size with clear contours along its course. The contents of the duct and the lesion of a suspension? pus? (Fig. 3). A fine needle aspiration biopsy was performed. Samples were taken for cytological examination.

Fig. 3. Ultrasound image of the left breast with an enlarged duct with heterogeneous contents

Fine needle aspiration biopsy results (05,22,2023): macrophages, papillary-like structures.

The results of a cytology of nipple of the left breast discharge (05,22,2023): structureless substance, single macrophages.

In connection with persistent pain syndrome and compaction of the breast, the patient independently sought a consultation with a surgeon at A.V. Vishnevsky National Medical Research Center of Surgery to determine further treatment tactics.

An outpatient examination was carried out.

Mammary glands Ultrasound (15.06.2023). In the projection of the central quadrant, an enlarged duct with a diameter of up to 5.0 mm is visualized with echo-

dense uniformly thickened walls, in which diffuse, increased echogenic content is determined (Fig. 4a). With duplex scanning, the blood flow in this area is not located. When examining the patient in the SMI mode, attention is drawn to the presence in the distal part of the dilated duct (in the area of narrowing) of an intraductal lesion with pronounced vascularization, and there is also an increase in the vascular pattern circularly in the walls of the duct in the area of expansion for up to 25.0 mm (Fig. 4b)). Conclusion: The ultrasound picture of the revealed changes allows us to suspect the presence of a lesion that compresses the duct (fibroadenoma?) with proximal dilatation and signs of inflammation.

Fig. 4. Ultrasound images of the dilated duct in the left breast; a - B-mode; b – in SMI mode (arrow indicates hypervascular lesion)

Laboratory parameters of blood and urine are within normal limits.

Based on the results of the examination, a preliminary diagnosis was made: intraductal papilloma. A decision was made on surgical treatment in the amount of sectoral resection of the left breast.

When hospitalized at A.V. Vishnevsky National Medical Research Center of Surgery, a standard medical history was taken: cerebral palsy.

Local status: mammary glands are symmetrical. The skin in the region of the left NAC is slightly hyperemic, light brown discharge is noted on palpation of the

nipple, as well as moderately painful induration of tissues behind the NAC up to 1.5 cm in size. The right mammary gland is without features. Regional lymph nodes are not enlarged.

Planned surgery (16.06.2023) **central resection of the left breast**. The operation was performed according to the standard scheme, without any special features.

The results of a planned histology (29.06.2023): the lesion of the mammary gland has the structure of a mixed fibroadenoma with focal proliferation of myoepithelium and structures of flowering adenosis (Fig. 5). **Conclusion:** morphological picture of mixed fibroadenoma of the left breast.

Fig. 5. Micrograph, stained with hematoxylin and eosin, x50 magnification. Mixed fibroadenoma with changes in the epithelium according to the type of blooming adenosis

The patient was discharged on the 4th day after the operation with recommendations for outpatient follow-up. At the control examination after two weeks, the wound healed by primary intention. There are no complaints.

In the presented clinical case, a fibroadenoma of a small size of the mammary gland, as it grew, squeezed the lactiferous duct with its retentional expansion, the addition of an infection, and the development of non-lactational mastitis. Conducted antibiotic therapy with the change of drugs didn't give an effect due to the presence of intraductal lesion and difficulty in secretion evacuation. Repeatedly performed ultrasound in B-mode + duplex scanning made it possible to diagnose dilation of the duct with its inhomogeneous contents, however, due to the resolving capabilities of the ultrasound scanner, it didn't allow visualizing the tumor. And only the use of SMI technology made it possible to intraductally localize the area of hypervascularization from microvessels, suspicious of neoplastic blood flow, which was later confirmed intraoperatively and morphologically verified as a tumor. We consider the presented case to be an important starting point for the application of the SMI technique for long-term non-lactational mastitis, with the possibility of detecting small tumors compressing the duct by ultrasound. SMI technology makes it possible to suspect and localize the area of the presence of a focal lesion of small sizes without radiation exposure and the use of echocontrast agents only within the framework of ultrasound.

Conclusion. Superb microvascular imaging (SMI) — is a relatively recently developed ultrasound diagnostic technology that aims to visualize blood flow in blood vessels at low velocity and small diameter. Unlike conventional Color and Power Doppler imaging, SMI can suppress the noise caused by motion artifacts without removing the weak signal from small blood flow, thus achieving higher sensitivity than duplex scanning. The article presents a clinical observation of a 33-year-old woman who has been unsuccessfully treated for 6 months for non-lactational mastitis caused by a small-sized mixed fibroadenoma that compresses and involves the gland duct. The SMI technology made it possible, without radiation exposure and the introduction of an echocontrast agent, to detect a small tumor that was not detected by ultrasound with standard technologies.

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